

Assessing the Viability of Bio-Pigment Watercolours as Substitutes for Acrylic-Based Poster Paints

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Abstract

Acrylic paints are a widespread and commonly used paint type due to their low cost and ease of use. However, acrylic paints cause significant harm to the environment. Acrylic paints are primarily composed of microplastics. Non-avoidable acts such as washing brushes, washing palettes, sanding, etc, release the microplastics within the paints into the environment. These microplastics can take several hundred years to decay naturally. Microplastics kill marine life and negatively affect terrestrial life. This paper aims to create and test bio-pigment-based watercolours and assess whether they are a viable alternative to acrylic paints. To create these natural watercolours, modern methods (i.e. enzyme-based pigment extraction) and traditional methods (i.e. mulling) were employed. Findings show that natural pigments ranging from yellow and blue to green can reasonably replace acrylic paints due to their colour, biodegradability, and ease of use. In contrast, the reds were hard to create as they are derived from acidic compounds requiring acidic binders to be stable; in contrast, all processes described in this paper used alkaline-based binders.

Keywords: Acrylic paints, Microplastics, Pollution, Biodegradable alternatives, Environmental impact

1. Introduction

Acrylic paints were a revolutionary paint type invented in the early 1900s. They are vibrant, quick-drying, hassle-free, easy-to-use paint artists can use. They required minimal clean-up as they could be washed away in water and did not leave any residue (unlike oil paints). This made them an ideal choice for artists and students. They were adopted by thousands of schools, art studios, hobbyists, and professional artists (Such as Andy Warhol, David Hockney, Helen Frankenthaler, etc). However, acrylic paints have a fatal flaw: they rely on an acrylic polymer binder (hence the name). The binder works by having microscopic plastics (specifically, particle sizes are both nanoscopic and microscopic; in this study, when

referring to microplastics, both microscopic and nanoscopic particles will be implied) dissolved in water. When dissolved, the acrylic particles can freely move around and be used for painting. Once the paint is applied, the water starts to evaporate, and the acrylic polymers start bonding to one another in hexagonal patterns. The acrylic polymer binder gives acrylic paints their characteristic quick drying time, strength, and flexibility (Liquitex, 2019). Here, we see the problem with acrylic paints. If the paint is reintroduced to water, all the microplastics eventually disperse out of the water and become extremely hard to remove. If a paint palette or brush containing acrylic paint is cleaned off under running water, then the microplastics enter the wastewater system. Here, they are extremely hard to separate out and wastewater processing facilities often cannot filter out the microplastic, and they leach into the ocean along with all the processed water. This entails that every time acrylic paints are used, some part of them will inevitably pollute the ocean. This affects not only marine life but also terrestrial life. Some smaller aquatic life can confuse the microplastics for food and consume it, where they get embedded within fish tissue and meat. Microplastics inhibit fish growth and negatively affect their metabolism (Li et al., 2021). If that fish is consumed by other life (i.e. larger fish, bears, humans, etc), then those microplastics can get into the bloodstream and flesh of the predator. In humans, microplastics were found in the bloodstream and the blood-brain barrier (Kopatz et al., 2023). Microplastics also negatively affect human metabolism, affect hormone production, cause reproductive disorders, and act like neurotoxins (Lee et al., 2023). Microplastics produced by acrylic paints can last in the ecosystem and food chain for hundreds of years before they biodegrade.

It is clear that acrylic paints require an eco-friendlier alternative. This paper aims to test the viability of organic, biodegradable paints against acrylic paints in applications like poster paints. The focus will primarily be on the paint's qualities and comparing those to acrylic paints. The created paints will be made from flowers, berries, and earth minerals. They will not contain any materials that will harm the environment / not biodegrade.

2. Materials and method

2.1 Materials:

The paints were crafted entirely from natural raw materials. Locally procured organic beetroot powder and charcoal was obtained from K-market (a regional chain of grocery stores) in Espoo, Finland. Additional organic components, including dried safflower petals, buckthorn seeds, bark from Brazilian redwood, and indigo powder, along with natural inorganic pigments like lapis lazuli, Venetian green Earth, Azurite powder, Moroccan yellow earth, red Moroccan earth, Yellow Moroccan earth, and Snaefellsjokull volcanic brownish-maroon earth, gum Arabic powder, gum Arabic-honey binder, calcium carbonate powder and linseed oil were acquired from Kremer Pigmente GmbH & Co. in Germany. Cellulase enzyme was sourced from Merk GmbH (Germany), and the cellulolytic enzyme cocktail (Viscozyme) from Novozyme.

2.2 Method:

2.2.1 Making Natural Poster Paints

Three principal methods were developed to extract pigments from natural raw materials and create natural and environmentally safe poster paints.

Water-based pigment extraction.

The method involved overnight soaking and boiling 50 g of the specified raw material in distilled water for 20 min to obtain a pigment-rich extract. Approximately 5 g of alum powder was added during the boiling of the soaked Brazilian redwood. The pigment slurry was then mixed with 5 g of gum Arabic powder, and powdered calcium carbonate was slowly added until a semisolid consistency was reached. The mixture was left to dry for 48-72 h, resulting in a solid paint block. The block was then cut into pieces to be used.

This method was used for the production of S-YC 2 (Safflower - Yellow Colour - 2) and BW-RC 1 (Brazilian Wood - Red Colour - 1). These paints were derived from dried safflower petals and the bark of Brazilian redwood trees.

1a

1b

Fig 1: (1a-b) Water-Based Pigment Extraction Methods. (1a) Production of Safflower Yellow colour S-YC 2 from dried safflower petals (1b) Production of Brazilian Wood Red Colour BW-RC1 from Brazilian redwood bark.

Enzyme-assisted pigment extraction

This method begins by heating 50 grams of the specified raw material in 200 ml of distilled water at 45 °C using a heated magnetic stirrer. Then, 1 ml of each cellulose and Viscozyme enzyme was added to the solution. For buckthorn, the seeds were ground into a fine powder and boiled in distilled water for 1h, and the solution was cooled to 45°C prior to adding the enzyme cocktail. Then, the mix was subjected to an incubation process within a 45°C water bath for one hour to activate the enzymes present. Following the incubation, the solution was cooled in an ice bath to inactivate the enzymes and then was subsequently filtered using a muslin cloth.

Following filtration, 5 grams of gum Arabic was added to the pigment-rich slurry. Then, calcium carbonate powder was gradually added until the mixture achieved a semisolid state. The mixture was then left undisturbed to dry for a period ranging between 48 to 72 hours, resulting in the formation of a solid paint block. This block was then cut into pieces, which were then used.

This enzyme-assisted pigment extraction method was employed to produce a variety of paints, including BR-RC 1 (Beet Root - Red Colour - 1), I-BC 1 (Indigo - Blue Colour - 1), BB-BC 1 (Blueberry - Blue Colour - 1), and BK-YC 1 (Buckthorn - Yellow Colour - 1). These paints were derived from beetroot powder, indigo leaf powder, blueberry powder, and buckthorn seeds (ground into powder).

2a

100% Natural, organic, green Indigo powder

Making an aqueous Indigo powder solution using a heated magnetic plate stirrer.

Indigo aqueous solution

Adding Enzyme 1 to the Indigo solution

Adding Enzyme 2 to the Indigo solution

Heating in a 45 °C water bath for 1 h.

Filtering the Indigo solution

Indigo pigment extract

Adding Calcium carbonate to the Indigo pigment

Indigo I-BC-1 paint

Indigo I-BC-1 paint turning blue in contact with atmospheric oxygen.

Dried Indigo I-BC-1 paint

Filter cloth dyed to a deep denim blue by the Indigo solution on drying.

100% natural blueberry powder

Preparing an aqueous solution

Adding gum Arabic and alum to the blueberry solution

Adding enzyme 1 to the blueberry solution

Adding enzyme 2 to the blueberry solution

Heating in a 45 °C water bath for 1 h

Filtering the enzyme treated blueberry solution

Blueberry pigment extract

Adding calcium carbonate to the blueberry extract

Blueberry BB-BC1 paint

2c

2d

Fig 2: (2 a-d) Enzyme-Assisted Pigment Extraction Processes. (2a) Production of BR-RC 1 (Beet Root Red Colour -1) from beet root powder. (2b) Production of I-BC 1 (Indigo-Blue Colour 1) from indigo leaf powder. (2c) Production of BB-BC 1 (Blueberry-Blue Colour 1) from blueberry powder. (2d) Production of BK-YC 1 (Buckthorn Yellow Colour 1) from buckthorn seed powder.

Mulling

The paint was produced in small batches using this technique. It required natural earth pigments to be mixed in a 1:5 ratio with calcium carbonate powder. Then, the mixture was poured into a pestle and mortar. 10 ml of a gum Arabic-honey binder were added to this mixture. Then the grinding process (mulling) began with the gradual addition of 30 millilitres of water, incorporated in increments of 10 ml, until the coarse earth pigment had been transformed into a smooth paste. Once mulling was complete, the semisolid paint was transferred into small rectangular plastic moulds, which were allowed to be set for 48 hours. Solid pigment-rich natural poster paints were obtained using this method.

The mulling technique had been utilized to produce colours such as E-RC 2 (Earth - Red Colour - 2), E-RY 1 (Earth - Yellow Colour - 1), LPL-BC 1 (Lapis Lazuli - Blue Colour 1), AZ-BC 1 (Azurite – Blue Colour - 1), CC-BC-1 (Charcoal – Black Colour – 1) and VE-GC 1 (Venetian Earth – Green Colour - 1) from respective pigments like Venetian red earth, Moroccan yellow earth, Lapis Lazuli powder, Azurite powder, Charcoal powder, and Venetian volcanic green earth (Verona green earth).

Furthermore, E-RC 1 (Earth - Red Colour - 1) was also created by mulling. However, it was a blend of three different earth pigments: natural red Moroccan earth, yellow Moroccan earth, and Snaefellsjokull volcanic brownish-maroon earth in a proportion of 2:1:1.

3a

3b

3c

Figure 3: (3a-d) Mulling technique. (3a) Production of E-RC 2 (Earth-red colour 2) from Venetian red earth. (3b) Production of E-RY 1 (Earth-yellow colour 1) from Moroccan yellow earth. (3c) Production of VE-GC 1 (Venetian green-colour 1) Venetian volcanic green earth (3d) Production of E-RC 1 (Earth-red colour 1) from Natural red Moroccan earth, Yellow Moroccan earth, and Snaefellsjokull volcanic brownish-maroon earth.

2.3 Qualitative testing of natural poster paints.

The colours created were categorized into three groups: Red, Blue-Green, and Yellow. A 20 x 20 cm stretched canvas sheet was used to test each colour group. Each canvas panel was equally divided into four to five sections, one for each paint, as marked by light pencil lines. Commercial acrylic poster paints from the same colour groups were used for qualitative comparison. Paint strips, each 4-5 cm wide, were then applied in both natural poster and acrylic forms across their designated sections, ensuring consistency in strip width and coating thickness. Following application, these strips were allowed to dry under controlled conditions (20 °C) for a period typically ranging between 24 to 48 hours. The dried paint strips underwent a thorough visual examination under consistent lighting to assess aspects such as colour vibrancy, surface texture, and differences in the finish between the paint types. A magnifying glass aided in detailed inspection. Additionally, tactile evaluations were conducted by gently feeling the texture and consistency of the paint strips, noting variations in smoothness, brush stroke visibility, and surface finish. The flexibility of the paints and their adhesion to the canvas were tested by gently bending the canvas observing any cracking, flaking, or detachment. A longevity and fade resistance test involved exposing the painted canvases to sunlight for 30 days to observe changes in colour and paint quality. Systematic documentation of observations was carried out on recording sheets, focusing on comparative analyses of colour retention, texture, adherence, and overall appearance. Qualitative conclusions were drawn based on the observed characteristics and performances of the paints on the canvas.

2.4 Demonstration of Paints during a school exhibition.

The natural poster paints, once prepared, were systematically organized into purpose-built metal boxes. Each box contained a set of 14 different colours arranged to facilitate students' convenience in using them. This set of 10 natural and eco-friendly paints was named 'Earth elements.'

Even though there is great interest in these diffusion models, a comprehensive taxonomy and analysis of the research progress on DMs are still lacking. Due to a great influx of contributions in this field of study, a comprehensive review and comparison of the existing literature would be beneficial and timely for the community. This study aims to provide a comprehensive overview/comparison of the Applications, Image Type, Image Augmentation, Competitiveness with other models (GANs, VAEs), limitations of DMs. This paper describes the challenges and issues, and identifies common trends that raise open questions about the future development of diffusion models both as algorithms and applications in the

Figure 4: 'Earth elements'; a set of 14 natural and eco-friendly poster paints created using natural materials as described in this paper.

Figure 5: Evaluation of Natural and Eco-friendly poster paints in various settings - Workshop, Art Class, and Project Exhibition - by 70 participants, including students and teachers.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Water-based pigment extraction

The research successfully showcased the efficacy of a water extraction method for deriving yellow pigment from dried safflower flowers and red pigment from Brazilian redwood bark. When the extracted yellow pigment from safflower was combined with calcium carbonate, the resulting colour, S-YC 2, was a paler yellow compared to the original pigment. Similarly, mixing red pigment from Brazilian redwood bark with calcium carbonate powder produced a rosy, pink hue, BW-RC 1, instead of red. Despite these alterations in colour, both S-YC 2 and BW-RC 1 were found to be pigment-rich, displaying distinct yellow and pink colours, respectively.

Pigments in plant cells are stored within specific structures, like chlorophyll in chloroplasts and carotenoids in chromoplasts, and humans have been extracting these pigments for over 10,000 years (Davies, 2004). Traditional water-based extraction methods have been used for creating textile and food dyes from plant materials (Miranda et al., 2021; Ragab et al., 2022). This method, however, is limited to water-soluble pigments and can lead to pigment decomposition due to boiling, thus yielding a limited amount of pigment (Ragab et al., 2022). To enhance the efficiency of

this method, plant materials are typically ground and soaked overnight to break down the cell structures holding the pigment molecules (Ragab et al., 2022).

This study innovatively applied the water-based pigment extraction technique for the first time in producing natural poster paints. The materials, including dried safflower and Brazilian redwood barks, were pre-soaked overnight before boiling to facilitate pigment release. However, boiling safflower petals for 20 minutes led to slight browning of the yellow pigment, suggesting that reducing the boiling time or using low heat might prevent pigment degradation.

Safflower has been used since ancient Egypt for fabric dyeing, particularly during mummification processes (Davies, 2004). Safflower contains two main pigments: yellow and red (Yan et al., 2022). The primary yellow pigments, hydroxysafflor yellow A and anhydrosafflor yellow B are water-soluble members of the quinochalcone flavonoid family and are used as food colourants (Yan et al., 2022). The red pigment carthamine, however, has poor water solubility (Yan et al., 2022). In this study, the yellow pigment was successfully extracted using the water-based method and transformed into a solid paint using calcium carbonate as a binder and carrier for use in natural poster paints. The production of safflower yellow poster paint is a labour-intensive process involving a 55-hour procedure that includes soaking, pigment extraction, and drying.

Regarding Brazilian redwood has been used since the Middle Ages as a key source for pink and red hues in inks, textiles, and oil paintings (Vitorino et al. 2016). The primary pigment found in this wood is brazilein, which is water soluble. (Vitorino et al., 2016). In this study, brazilein was successfully extracted as a lake pigment into a concentrated red slurry by boiling it with alum. Interestingly, when the pigment-rich slurry was mixed with alkaline calcium carbonate, a shift in the final colour to pink was observed. This transformation in colour can likely be linked to the modification in pH levels resulting from the addition of calcium carbonate. According to the study by Vitorino et al. (2016) on the production of brazilwood lake pigments using historically accurate methods, this variation in hue is a consequence of brazilein's reaction to different pH environments. Specifically, Brazilein shows a red colour in acidic conditions (pH 0.5-3.5), shifts to rose pink at a pH range of 6.5-6.9 and attains a purple shade at a pH of 9.7.

Therefore, in this study, the water-based extraction technique was effectively used to create natural and environmentally friendly light yellow and pink poster paints.

4.2 Enzyme-assisted pigment extraction

The study demonstrated that extracting pigments using enzymes from sources like beetroot, indigo, blueberries, and buckthorn seeds resulted in more vivid colours than traditional water-based methods. This enzymatic technique was also more efficient, needing only 45°C for processing compared to 100°C for water extraction, and took 50 hours instead of 55. The enzymatic process preserved the pigments without degradation, although buckthorn seeds required an initial boiling step in water for an hour before the enzyme treatment. However, incorporating calcium carbonate powder into the enzyme-extracted pigment slurries altered the final colours of the paints. Specifically, the beetroot pigment, originally deep red, resulted in a flesh pink shade in the final BB-RC 1 paint. Indigo led to a light grey-blue colour in the I-BC 1 paint, while blueberry produced a dark grey-blue hue in the BB-BC 1 paint. Notably, buckthorn seeds yielded a very vibrant yellow colour in the BK-YC 1 paint, demonstrating a significant impact of the calcium carbonate additive on the colour outcomes.

This research utilized an enzyme extraction technique involving cellulase and a commercially available cellulolytic enzyme blend known as Viscozyme. Cellulolytic enzymes break down plant cell walls, enhancing their permeability and

leading to an increased pigment yield (Miranda et al., 2021). While these enzymes are typically used in extracting flavours from plant materials (Miranda et al., 2021), this study successfully applied them to extract pigments for creating natural and environmentally friendly poster paints.

Building on the previously mentioned enzyme extraction process, it's crucial to consider the chemical properties of the specific pigments involved. For instance, betanin, which is the main pigment in beetroot, has a distinct red-violet hue (Devadiga & Ahipa, 2020). However, betanin's colour strength is known to decrease in environments with a pH higher than 5 (Devadiga & Ahipa, 2020). This aspect of betanin's chemistry could explain why the addition of alkaline calcium carbonate to the red-violet beetroot pigment resulted in a flesh-pink colour in the final product.

Indigo pigment, indigotin, also has unique chemical characteristics. Historically renowned for providing various shades of blue to textiles and artworks, indigo was a popular choice in regions like India, China, and Egypt (Ferreira et al., 2004). The formation of indigo dye involves complex reduction and oxidation reactions, where both pH and oxygen levels play a critical role in determining its blue colour (Ferreira et al., 2004). In its soluble form, indigo exists as leucoindigo, which is colourless in a reduced state (Ferreira et al., 2004). However, upon exposure to air, it undergoes oxidation and transforms into a blue hue (Ferreira et al., 2004). Alkaline conditions can create a reducing environment, leading to the loss of oxygen molecules in the indigotin and the formation of colourless leucoindigo (Ferreira et al., 2004). This chemical process likely accounts for the faint blue colour of the I-BC 1 paint, which resulted from adding alkaline calcium carbonate to the deep bluish-green, indigo pigment slurry. Consequently, the specific chemical processes necessary to produce Indigo meant that using natural indigo leaf powder to create a deep blue poster paint was not effective. Nonetheless, experimenting with pre-oxidized blue indigo powder might yield more successful and promising results.

Additionally, the pigment anthocyanin, found in blueberries, displays a diverse range of colours based on the pH level (Wahyuningsih et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2022). Anthocyanins, which are derivatives of flavonoids – a broad category of water-soluble plant pigments – change colour depending on the acidity or alkalinity of their environment (Wahyuningsih et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2022). At an acidic pH of 2-3, anthocyanin appears red; it turns pink in a slightly less acidic pH of 4-6, becomes purple at a neutral to slightly alkaline pH of 7-8, and shifts to blue at a highly alkaline pH of 9-11 (Wahyuningsih et al., 2017). This shift in colour explains why the initially deep red blueberry pigment slurry turned into the final blue BB-BC 1 poster colour upon addition of alkaline calcium carbonate powder. To achieve a red paint from blueberries, using acidic or neutral cellulose powder as an alternative to calcium carbonate could be a solution. However, this substitution might lead to increased production costs for the poster paint.

Further, the BK-YC 1 colour extracted from buckthorn seeds using an enzyme-based method exhibited a deep yellow hue and demonstrated stability upon the incorporation of calcium carbonate. A study on targeted metabolome and transcriptome analysis of sea buckthorn by (Liang et al., 2022) suggests that this yellow colouration is likely attributed to a blend of various compounds, including flavonoids, zeaxanthin, lutein, and a range of other carotene pigments. Notably, the carotene pigments are known to show considerable resistance to changes under heat or acidic environments (Chandra et al., 2021; Lakshmi & Saraswathy, 2019). However, a marginal reduction in the intensity of the yellow colour was noted under alkaline conditions (Chandra et al., 2021; Lakshmi & Saraswathy, 2019).

4.3 Mulling

The scientific study revealed that the creation of poster paints using earth pigments, specifically E-RC2, E-RY1, LPL-BC 1, AZ-BC 1, VE-GC, and E-RC, yielded vibrant hues of red, yellow ochre, sky blue, cobalt blue, jade green, and maroon-brown, respectively. The mulling technique, which involved labour-intensive hand grinding of pigments in small

batches, was essential to attain a smooth consistency and texture in the paints. This method, though time-consuming, was more efficient than previous techniques, requiring a total of 49 hours, which is shorter than the 55 hours needed for water-based extraction and the 50 hours for enzyme-assisted pigment extraction. Notably, earth pigments facilitated the easy production of challenging colours like green, blue and red, which were hard to achieve with plant-based raw materials.

The distinctive colours of earth pigments are influenced by their mineral compositions, which vary according to their geographical origins (Corteza et al., 2022). For instance, Venetian red earth, known for its warm, rich red tone, derives this colour from hematite found in Italy's Vento region (O'Hanlon, 2023a). This pigment, prominent during the Italian Renaissance, was utilized not just in paintings but also in brickmaking in Venice (O'Hanlon, 2023a). Moroccan ocher, characterized by its golden-yellow hue, is composed of a mineral matrix known as limonite, a type of hydrous ferric oxide, with goethite being the dominant mineral (Greenleaf, 2023). This particular earth pigment, hailing from Midelt in central Morocco, has been traditionally used in waterproof wall plaster called Tadelakt (Greenleaf, 2023). Lapis lazuli, a gemstone cherished for its intense ultramarine blue colour, owes its hue to the mineral lazurite (de Mairo, 2023). This pigment has been used in various artworks, from Egyptian tombs and Persian and Mughal miniatures to the creations of Renaissance masters like Giotto di Bondone (de Mairo, 2023). Azurite blue, a crucial pigment in medieval European paintings, was favoured for its affordability and availability compared to lapis lazuli (O'Hanlon, 2022). Its vibrant blue colour comes from copper carbonate (O'Hanlon, 2022). Verona green earth from Italy, with its greyish green shade, contains the clay mineral celadonite, found in the volcanic basalt areas of Verona, and was used in ancient Roman art, including Pompeii frescoes (O'Hanlon, 2023b). Moroccan red earth, sourced from central Morocco's Midelt region, features a reddish-brown colour due to hematite or dehydrated iron oxide and has been a part of plastering and medieval European paintings (Corteza et al., 2022).

Natural earths, primarily made up of minerals, are advantageous for producing stable colours like green, red, and blue, as they are lightfast, opaque, and resistant to environmental conditions like pH and redox changes (Corteza et al., 2022). In contrast, achieving these colours from plant-based pigments can be challenging. Chlorophyll, for example, is prone to photo-oxidative destruction under sunlight and sensitive to pH changes, as are the red anthocyanin and blue indigo pigments (Chandra et al., 2021; Lakshmi & Saraswathy, 2019).

Given the crystalline nature of the minerals in earth pigments, the mulling technique, which grinds these minerals into amorphous powders, is essential. This process was employed in this study to ensure a smooth and consistent texture in the resulting paints.

The practice of employing earth pigments for artistic purposes dates back to the dawn of human artistry, evident in prehistoric cave paintings and extending through various ancient civilizations, including Egyptian, Greek, and Indian art, as well as in sculptures and architectural designs (Corteza et al., 2022). Despite this rich history, the advent of modern mass-produced and user-friendly mediums like acrylic paints led to a decline in the traditional art of crafting and utilizing earth pigments. In recent times, however, there's been a growing awareness and preference among consumers for eco-friendly art materials. This shift in mindset is contributing to a renewed interest and significance in the use of earth pigments in contemporary art. In this study, a dedicated effort was undertaken to create poster paints using earth pigments, which culminated in the successful production of six distinct colors, as mentioned above.

4.4 Qualitative testing of natural poster paints

Fig 6: (6a-c) Comparative evaluation of Natural pigment colours vs acrylic paints. (6a) Natural paints BR-RC 1, BW-RC 1, E-RB-1 and E-RC 2. (6b) Acrylic paints flesh pink, baby pink, brown and red

(6c) Natural paints BB-BC1, I-BC1, LPL-BC1, AZ-BC1, VE-GC1. (6d) Acrylic paints Deep cyan-purple, Cerulean blue-white, cyan blue, Cerulean blue, Sap green

(6e) Comparison of safflower S-YC 2, Buckthorn BK-YC1, Moroccan earth E-YC1 and acrylic medium yellow paint on a canvas block

6c

In a comparative analysis of natural poster paints and acrylic paints, this study revealed striking similarities in various attributes. The natural paints, developed from a blend of organic and mineral pigments, closely matched the hue and intensity of their acrylic counterparts. This similarity was particularly evident in the primary colour families—reds, greens, blues, and yellows.

The natural BB-RC 1 paint exhibited a flesh pink shade, akin to the acrylic version made from Burnt sienna and white. Similarly, the BW-RC 1 paint's baby-pink hue was identical to a blend of acrylic magenta and white. The brown E-RC 1 paint, derived from a mix of earth pigments, paralleled the acrylic shade made from Burnt sienna and Burnt umber. A slight variation was observed in the E-RC 2 paint, which presented a brown-tinged red, closely resembling an acrylic blend of Brilliant red and Burnt Sienna.

This study also covered a range of other shades. BB-BC-1's purple grey mirrored the acrylic mix of Deep Cyan and Purple. LPL-BC 1's rich cyan blue and AZ-BC 1's light blue were comparable to respective acrylic hues. VE-GC 1's moss green resembled acrylic sap green mixed with white. In the yellow spectrum, S-YC 2's Safflower yellow was lighter than acrylic lemon yellow, while BK-YC 1's deep yellow closely matched acrylic bright yellow. E-YC 1's yellow ochre was identical to the acrylic yellow ochre.

Beyond colour comparisons, the study extended to tactile qualities, adhesion, flexibility, and durability. Both paint types exhibited similar smoothness and consistency, adhering well to canvas with minimal cracking or flaking. However, the Lapis Lazuli paint (LPL-BC 1) exhibited a rough texture, making it challenging to apply. This was attributed to inadequate grinding of the LPL-BC 1 paint during the mulling process, resulting in a coarser texture due to the presence of microcrystals. Most of the paints also demonstrated equivalent longevity and fade resistance under sunlight exposure over a duration of 30 days. The only exception was the S-YC 2 paint, which demonstrated inferior lightfastness, leading to fading within the 30-day period. This fading issue is linked to the physical and chemical properties of the colour compound in S-YC 2, suggesting that the observed performance cannot be attributed to method errors (Lee et al., 2023).

This study's findings challenge the conventional preference for acrylic paints, demonstrating that natural poster paints, with their comparable colour vibrancy, texture, and durability, can be effective alternatives for various artistic applications. The use of calcium carbonate as a pigment carrier in these natural paints contributed to their opacity. At the same time, the inclusion of gum Arabic and a gum Arabic honey binder enhanced adherence and reduced paint cracking.

The observations are supported by the fact that a significant number of ancient Egyptian paintings, which predominantly utilized natural pigments, have exhibited exceptional stability over a span exceeding 3,000 years (Muffet, 2019a). Despite the susceptibility of organic compounds to photodegradation under prolonged exposure to sunlight, many ancient artworks, including Greek frescoes and cave paintings shielded from solar exposure, have retained their visual splendour (Muffet, 2019b). These artworks demonstrate a sophisticated use of natural mineral and plant-based pigments, often combined with binders such as limestone, egg tempera, or natural gums (Muffet, 2019a).

4.5 Demonstration of Paints during a school exhibition

Figure 7: Participants Engaging in Artwork Creation Using Eco-Friendly Poster Paints Formulated in Current Research.

Throughout the 2022-23 academic year, a series of demonstrations at the International School of Helsinki effectively showcased the educational and interactive value of natural poster paints in an educational setting (Fig 7). These demonstrations, including a workshop, an art class, and a project exhibition, engaged seventy participants comprising teachers and students. The students interacted with the paints, exploring various colours and brush techniques. Observations focused on the texture, and colour quality of the paints. Feedback from students and teachers alike was overwhelmingly positive, highlighting aspects such as smooth application, vibrant colours, quick drying time, and overall performance of the paints. This study underscores the effectiveness of integrating eco-friendly art materials into promoting sustainable practices in art. The positive reception and results from these demonstrations suggest the potential for broader implementation of such eco-friendly art materials in educational institutions worldwide, fostering creativity and environmental awareness among students. The most common feedback was about the LPL-BC 1 paint, which was generally found to be more difficult to use compared to other paints. Additionally, a few individuals noted that the E-RC 2 paint tended to appear more orange than red.

4. Conclusion

In summary, applying the methods described above and assessing through various comparative and longevity tests, we have successfully developed an extensive range of organic, biodegradable, non-toxic poster paints. These paints match the qualities of acrylics but are made from environmentally friendly materials. Despite some paints, specifically I-BC 1, LPL-BC 1, and S-YC 2, not performing as well in certain tests, the majority (10 paints) proved successful. Practical demonstrations provided valuable insights and overwhelmingly positive feedback, indicating a potential global demand for such organic paints. Students also appreciated the carrying case provided with the paints, finding it to be both compact and practical in design. Future research could explore more organic materials and experiment with cellulose-based binders to create acidic mediums, allowing the creation of a broader spectrum of red pigments. Additionally, enzyme-based pigment extraction methods could enable the use of various plant-based materials, such as rhubarb or fruit scraps, for pigment production.

This study aims to rejuvenate interest in ancient paint-making techniques, kick-starting the development of sustainable paints that could potentially replace acrylics. Such innovation is crucial for preserving marine ecosystems and, ultimately, benefiting humanity.

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